

A CLINICAL CASE REPORT FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF SHALAKYA TANTRA ON DANTAHARSHA

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ABSTRACT

Background: *Dantaharsha* is among Eight *Dantaroga* explained by *Acharya Sushruta* out of seven *Ayatana* of *Mukha* and is most common disorder of the mouth. It is characterized by acute or chronic dental stimuli or intolerance to thermal, chemical or tactile stimulus. Clinically if teeth do not tolerate heat or cold or any other kind of touch it is known as *Dantaharsha*. In Modern Dentistry it can be correlated with Dentinal Hypersensitivity. The causes, prevention and treatment all are explained in details in the classical texts.

Material and Methods: This is a case report of a female patient aged 28 years, who came to Shalaky Tantra Dental OPD, complaining of hypersensitivity of multiple teeth and gums of both upper and lower jaw for 4 months. On examination of oral cavity, the oral hygiene was found to be

poor and there was generalized gum recession and root exposure. This case report highlights the successful management of *Dantaharsha* through Ayurvedic Intervention such as *Gandusha*, *Kavala* and *Vata Shamaka* therapy which were given for 21 days. **Result:** The patient showed significant improvement in assessment criteria. **Discussion:** *Dantaharsha* is *Vata Dosha pradhana vyadhi* so *Vatahara* treatment was opted for the management of the same. So, by effect of formulations and procedures *Dantaharsha* management showed significant result.

KEYWORDS: *Dantaharsha*, *Shalaky tantra*, *Ayatana*, Dentinal Hypersensitivity, *Gandusha*, *Kavala*.

INTRODUCTION

In *Shalaky Tantra* total 7 *Ayatana* or *Adhithana* were mentioned for *Mukharoga*.^[1] *Mukha* is considered as one of the *Nava Dwara*. There are various diseases affecting *Mukha* and parts of *Mukha* i.e *Ayatana*. According to *Acharya Sushruta* these are *Oshthagata*, *Dantamoolagata*, *Dantagata*, *Jihvagata*, *Talugata*, *Kanthagata* and *Sarvasara Mukharoga*^[2]; while *Acharya Vagbhatta* added *Gandagata Mukharoga*^[3] as eighth *Ayatana*. *Dantaharsha* is among eight *Dantaroga* mentioned in almost all Ayurveda texts and Acharyas. It is the disease in which teeth do not tolerate *Sheeta* (cold), *Ushna* (heat), *Madhura* (sweet), *Amla* (sour) or any other kind of stimulus hence known as *Dantaharsha*.^[4] Good oral hygiene is more important than just daily routine as over the past decade, researchers have shown that bad oral hygiene can trigger immune system which can lead to many serious complications. Neglecting oral care can increase risk of heart disease and stroke.^[5] Dentine hypersensitivity is characterized by rapid, short, sharp pain arising from exposed dentin in response to the stimuli typically thermal, evaporative, tactile, osmotic, or chemical. The most commonly involved teeth are buccal surfaces of premolars and labial surfaces of incisors. In Ayurveda *Dantaswasthaya* was explained very clearly, even mentioned and obliged in *Dincharya* too. The condition arises mainly due to vitiation of *Vata Dosha*, often associated with *Pitta*, affecting *Danta* and its supporting structure.

CASE REPORT

A 28-year-old female patient presented with complaints of sharp pain and hypersensitivity of multiple teeth and gums on intake of cold water, sour and sweet food items for 4 months. The pain was sudden, sharp, short lasting and localized. Patient also had severe problem of acidity and constipation.

HISTORY- Poor oral hygiene

Frequent consumption of cold beverages

Improper brushing technique

History of past illness- Same complaints 1 year ago. Patient took Modern medicine and cared about dental hygiene for some time and got relief temporarily.

FAMILY HISTORY – None

PERSONAL HISTORY

Diet- Nonvegetarian

Bowel- Constipation

Addiction- Nil

Appetite- Good

Sleep- Disturbed sometime

AGGRAVATING FACTORS

Sour, sweet, cold food items

Acidity

SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION

Mild constipation

Severe acidity

DENTAL EXAMINATION

Oral hygiene- Poor

Colour- Staining of teeth

Contour- Altered

Dental caries- Nil

Bleeding per gums- Nil

EXPOSURE OF ROOT

Apical																
Middle			+			+					+					
Cervical						+				+						
	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Cervical		+	+						+	+						
Middle						+				+						
Apical																

CONSISTENCY

Hard						+										
Soft				+					+	+			+	+		
Firm		+	+										+	+		
	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Firm		+		+	+	+			+	+	+					
Soft					+	+							+			
Hard																

EROSION

				+	+			+	+	+					
8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
					+	+			+	+		+			

ASSESEMENT CRITERIA**Subjective criteria**

Parameters	Intensity of <i>Dantaharsha</i> (Before Treatment)
Intolerance to cold items	Present
Intolerance to sweet and sour items	Present
Acidity	Severe
Improper Brushing	Present
Poor oral hygiene	Present

Objective criteria

Parameter	Intensity of <i>Dantaharsha</i> (Before treatment)
Pain on percussion	Present

DRUG FORMULATION USED

1. *Deepana- Pachana- Erandabhrishta Haritaki* 1 teaspoon with lukewarm water at night time.
2. *Dashmoola Kwatha+ Irimedadi Taila- Kavala*
3. *Nimba, Guduchi, Triphala, Khadira churna- Pratisarana*
4. *Dashanasanskara churna- Manjana*
5. *Mahanarayana Taila- Gandusha*

INTERVENTIONS

No.	Drugs	Dose	Route	Duration
1	<i>Erandabhrishta Haritaki</i> with lukewarm water	1 Teaspoon	Oral	7 days
	<i>Dashmoola Kwatha</i> (Lukewarm) with 2 teaspoon <i>Irimedadi Taila</i> ^[6]	Mouth full Twice daily	<i>Kavala</i>	
	<i>Nimba, Guduchi, Triphala, Khadira Churna</i>	Q.S.	<i>Pratisarana</i>	
	<i>Dashanasanskara Churna</i>	Q.S.	<i>Manjana</i>	
2	<i>Dashmoola Kwatha</i> (Lukewarm) with 2 teaspoon <i>Irimedadi Taila</i> ^[7]	Mouth full Twice daily	<i>Kavala</i>	7 days
	<i>Nimba, Guduchi, Triphala, Khadira Churna</i>	Q.S.	<i>Pratisarana</i>	
	<i>Dashanasanskara Churna</i>	Q.S.	<i>Manjana</i>	
3	<i>Mahanarayana Taila</i> ^[8]	Mouth full Twice daily	<i>Gandusha</i>	7 days

RESULTS

After 21 days of treatment, both subjective and objective parameters showed significant improvement.

SUBJECTIVE CRITERIA

Parameters	Intensity of <i>Dantaharsha</i> (After Treatment)
Intolerance to cold items	Improved
Intolerance to sweet and sour items	Improved
Acidity	Minimal
Improper Brushing	Improved
Poor oral hygiene	Improved

OBJECTIVE CRITERIA

Parameter	Intensity of <i>Dantaharsha</i> (After treatment)
Pain on percussion	Absent

DISCUSSION

Dantaharsha is a *Vata* predominant *Vata- Pittaja* condition mentioned in *Ayurveda Samhitas*, is a common dental problem characterised by sharp shooting pain associated with intolerance of teeth to exposure of wind (*pravata*), sour taste (*amla*), cold food items (*sheeta bhakshya padartha*) and on intake of sour food items (*amlaashana*). As mentioned in *Susrutha Samhita Uttaratantra Upadravika Adyaya*, the best treatment for any condition is *Nidana Parivarjana*. So, in this condition, the first step towards the management is avoidance of the aggravating factors like *Pravata, Amla, and Sheeta Bhakshana. Gandusha, Kavala* plays vital role in the management of *Dantaharsha*. Considering the special indication of *Irimedadi Taila* as *Visheshata Dantarogajit* and the indication of *Gandusha* and *Kavala* in the management of *Dantaharsha*, here in this case *Irimedadi Taila Kavala* along with *Vatahara Dasamoola Kwatha* was used, which gave significant result. *Nimba, Guduchi, Triphala, Khadira Churna* used for *Pratisarana* over gums all are having anti- inflammatory, anti-microbial, *Ropana* (healing), resistance, Anti-oxidant and *Stambhana* properties. Basically, these *Churna* has *Kashaya Rasa* dominance which closes dentinal tubules, *Tikta Rasa* which reduces inflammation and also relieves sensitivity and *Ropana- Rasayana* effect which gives long term healing. *Mahanarayana taila* is known for its benefits in supporting musculoskeletal health and alleviating *Vata*-related disorders, thus helpful in strengthening and *Vatahara* properties which are beneficial in *Dantaharsha*.

CONCLUSION

The management of *Dantaharsha* includes all *Vatahara* and also *Pittahara* treatments like *Dashmoola kwatha Kavala* along with *Irimedadi Taila*. *Irimedadi Taila* is explained in *Sarangadhara Samhita madhyamah khanda* under —*Taila kalpana* 'for *Mukha* and *Danta Roga*. *Nimba*, *Guduchi*, *Triphala*, *Khadira Churna* giving relief with *Pratisarana* having anti- inflammatory, anti- microbial and strengthening properties. *Gandushadharana* with *Mahanarayana Taila* is beneficial due to its *Vatahara* properties. *Gandusha* is specially mentioned in the management of *Dantaharsha*, and as per *Susruta Samhita*^[9], while *Dashanasanskara Churna* is classical remedy for *Dantagataroga*. The treatment gave significant relief in *Dantaharsha*.

LIMITATION OF STUDY

As this is a single case report there is a need of study to be conducted on a larger population for establishing good protocol.

REFERENCES

1. Sushruta Samhita – Ayurveda tattva sandipika commentary by Dr Ambika Datta Shastri, Chaukhambha samskrit samsthan, Varanasi, Purvardha Mukha Roga Vigyaniaya Adhyaya, 16/3; P. 381.
2. Sushruta Samhita – Ayurveda tattva sandipika commentary by Dr Ambika Datta Shastri, Chaukhambha samskrit samsthan, Varanasi, Purvardha Mukha Roga Vigyaniaya Adhyaya, 16/3; P. 381
3. Ashtanga Hridayam-Vidyotini commentary by Kaviraja Atrideva Gupta, Chaukhambha Prakashan Varanasi, Uttartantra, Mukha Roga Vijyaniam 22/64-65; P. 714
4. Sushruta. Sushruta samhita – English translation and edited by P.V. Sharma, Reprint. Varanasi: Chowkhambha visvabharati; 2005. Vol.2. P. 563.
5. Li, X., Kolltveit, K. M., Tronstad, L., & Olsen, I. (2000). Systemic Diseases Caused by Oral Infection. *Clinical Microbiology Reviews*, 13(4), 547–558; 15 Diseases Caused by Poor Dental Hygiene
6. Author- R. Vidyanath, Co-author- K. Nishteswar, Chaukhambha krishnadas academy Sanskrit series Varanasi, second edition 2008 Sahasrayoga, Tailayogaparakarna 57/90-96.
7. Author- R. Vidyanath, Co-author- K. Nishteswar, Chaukhambha krishnadas academy Sanskrit series Varanasi, second edition 2008 Sahasrayoga, Tailayogaparakarna 57/90-96.

8. Bhashajya ratnavali Bhapa commentary by Pandit Saryuprasad Tripathi and Kaviraja Pandit Gopalprasad Sharma Kaushik, Vata Rogaadhikar, Shlok Sankhya-93-105; Mahanarayana Thailam – Benefits, Uses, Ingredients & Side Effects | Ask Ayurveda
9. Susruta Samhita of Susruta with the Nibandhasangraha Commentary of Sri Dalhanacharya and the Nyayacandrika Panjika of Sri Gayadasacharya on Nidanasthana, Edited by Vaidya Yadavji Trikamji Acharya and Narayan Ram Acharya ‘Kavyatirtha’, Chikitsasthana 22/34, Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, Reprint edition, 2021; P. 493.